

Calculation of DPA for the VVER-1200 Reactor Vessel

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Neutron irradiation damage is of the most critical damage mechanisms in reactor vessel (RV) steel. Neutrons transfer their kinetic energy to target atoms of RV steel that start to jump creating vacancies and interstitials known as Frenkel Pairs (FP). The FPs are responsible for formation of defected clusters and microstructural modifications. These effects deteriorate physical and mechanical properties of the RV steels among which results in limiting the lifetime of reactor vessel. The most sensitive location in the RV related neutron irradiation damages is the area adjacent to the middle of the reactor core. In this paper, Monte Carlo simulation of the detailed reactor core have led to identifying the areas maximum neutron flux in the RV. Then the SRIM/TRIM Monte Carlo codes are used to evaluate the neutron spectral-averaged Displacements Per Atom (DPA) values for the RV region with the most intense neutron irradiation.

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1. Introduction

The safe and reliable operation of nuclear power plants necessitates the preservation of the structural integrity of the reactor vessel material throughout the reactor's operational lifespan. The degradation of the reactor vessel steel is a complex process influenced by various factors, including thermal treatment and radiation exposure. This degradation also depends on the chemical composition, manufacturing conditions, and post-production processing of the material. Neutron radiation damage is one of the most critical factors contributing to RV steel degradation [1, 2]. The fast neutrons to material structure interaction processes generate modification of the mechanical properties (decrease of toughness, increase of yield stress, hardness, and tensile

strength) The most impactful in this process are fast neutrons generated during the fission reaction. Neutrons transfer their kinetic energy to the atoms in the medium, displacing them from their lattice positions and imparting enough energy to displace additional atoms, thereby creating vacancies and what are known as Frenkel Pairs (FP) (see Figure 1).

FIG. 1. (Color online) A Frenkel defect in the crystal lattice.

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FPs are responsible for the formation of defect clusters and the modification of the microstructure (such as phase reactions and

segregations). These effects degrade the physical and mechanical properties of reactor vessel steels, which limits the reactor vessel's service life. The measure of defect accumulation is the Displacements Per Atom (DPA), which indicates the number of defects per atom in the material.

This work is dedicated to developing methods for calculating the DPA in the reactor vessel using Monte Carlo methods. It also involves calculating the DPA in VVER-1200 reactor vessel using certified and accessible programs: Serpent [3], MCNP4B [4], and Srim/Trim [5].

2. Energy spectrum of neutron flux at the inner boundary of the VVER-1200 reactor vessel

To determine the DPA (Displacements Per Atom), it is essential to have the neutron flux spectrum at the inner boundary of the reactor vessel. This spectrum was obtained using a developed model of the VVER-1200 reactor with the SERPENT code [3]. The reactor model is shown in Figure 2.

FIG. 2. (Color online) VVER-1200 Model (cross-section at half the height of the core) used for the spectrum calculation with the Serpent code.

The calculated neutron flux spectrum at the reactor vessel of the VVER-1200 is shown in Figure 3.

This spectrum was directly utilized in the simulation of neutron interactions with the reactor vessel to obtain primary knock-on atoms.

FIG. 3. (Color online) Neutron flux spectrum at the inner boundary of the reactor vessel, used in MCNP4B.

FIG. 4. Kinematics of recoil nucleus formation; n_0 is the primary neutron, n is the scattered neutron, A_r is the recoil atom.

It was initially converted into a continuous function form, then re-digitized with a uniform step and translated into probability per interval, which is necessary for the MCNP4B program [4]. During the simulation, the following composition of VVER-1200 reactor vessel steel (15H2NMFA) was used [6]:

Table 1. Composition of the VVER-1200 Reactor Vessel Steel (composition in %).

Element	Fe	C	Si	Cr	Mn	Ni	Mo
Weight Percentage	95.0	0.18	0.31	1.97	0.44	1.19	0.52

3. Calculation of the distribution of primary knock-on atoms

Using the neutron flux spectrum in MCNP4B, a *PTRAC* file was generated for a steel vessel with a thickness of 20 cm. This file

contained the coordinates of neutron interaction points with atoms, the types of these atoms, the momentum of neutrons, and their energy after collision. A single neutron could generate multiple primary knock-on atoms (PKAs). For further calculations, information about the PKAs (their type, birth coordinates, energy, and momentum direction) was needed instead of the neutron data. Conservation laws in binary collisions were employed for this purpose. These calculations were performed using a Mathematica (Wolfram) script. The kinematics of the formation of a recoil nucleus is shown in Figure 4.

Based on conservation laws, the following can be written:

$$E_A = E_n^0 - E_n, \quad \vec{P}_A = \vec{P}_n^0 - \vec{P}_n, \quad (1)$$

where E_A , P_A are energy and momentum of the recoil atom, E_n^0 , P_n^0 are energy and momentum of the incident neutron, E_n , P_n are energy and momentum of the scattered neutron.

The unit vector along the momentum of the recoil nucleus, included in the *TRIM.dat* file, is defined by the equation:

$$\vec{n}_A = \frac{\vec{P}_n^0 - \vec{P}_n}{|\vec{P}_n^0 - \vec{P}_n|} = \frac{\vec{P}_n^0 - \vec{P}_n}{\sqrt{P_n^0{}^2 - 2(\vec{P}_n^0 \vec{P}_n) + P_n^2}},$$

$$\vec{P}_n^0 = \sqrt{2E_n^0 m} \vec{n}_0, \quad \vec{P}_n = \sqrt{2E_n m} \vec{n}. \quad (2)$$

where m is the neutron mass, \vec{n}_0 is the unit vector along the momentum of the primary neutron, \vec{n} is the unit vector along the momentum of the scattered neutron, \vec{n}_A is the unit vector along the momentum of the recoil nucleus.

After simple transformations, we get:

$$\vec{n}_A = \frac{\vec{n}_0 \sqrt{E_n^0} - \vec{n} \sqrt{E_n}}{\sqrt{E_n^0 + E_n - 2\sqrt{E_n^0 E_n} (\vec{n}_0 \vec{n})}} \quad (3)$$

These equations determine all the necessary parameters of the recoil nucleus for the *TRIM.dat*

file. Subsequently, the SRIM/TRIM program used this file to calculate the number of vacancies per ion and per angstrom of trajectory.

Figure 5 shows the distribution curves of vacancies across the reactor vessel wall depth, generated by various PKAs, scaled per incident neutron. Figure 6 presents the vacancy distribution curves across the reactor vessel wall depth, generated by different PKAs, scaled per incident neutron in one cm³ over one year of reactor operation.

FIG. 5. Number of vacancies per angstrom per corresponding PKA.

FIG. 6. Number of vacancies per cm³ accumulated over one year per corresponding PKA.

Next, the number of vacancies per ion-angstrom was recalculated into *DPA* according to the following algorithm:

Calculation of *DPA* per neutron for recoil nucleus type i :

$$\text{DPA}^i = \frac{N^i \cdot \text{vac}^i}{NPS \cdot N_A^i} 10^8 \text{ (defect/atom} \cdot \text{sec)}, \quad (4)$$

where: N_i are number of ions of type i in the initial *PTRAC* file, vac^i are number of vacancies per angstrom created by an ion of type i , N_A^i are number of atoms of type i in 1 cm^3 of the medium, NPS are number of simulated histories in generating the *PTRAC* file.

Total DPA per simulated neutron is determined by:

$$\text{DPA} = \sum_i^{N_a} \text{DPA}_i, \quad (5)$$

where N_a is the number of types of atoms in the medium.

DPA created by neutron flux with density n ($1 \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{sec}^{-1}$) over time t :

$$\text{DPA}_f = \text{DPA} \cdot n \cdot t \quad (6)$$

Figure 7 shows the DPA created in the reactor vessel by the primary ion (Fe) at different depths of the vessel. Similarly, Figure 8 shows the DPA for all ions. The difference is minimal as iron ions contribute the most.

FIG. 7. DPA distribution across the vessel wall depth from Fe ions.

Results for the VVER-1200 (number of simulated neutrons $NPS = 5 \times 10^6$), averaged over 10 mm, are presented in Figure 9.

FIG. 8. DPA distribution across the vessel wall depth from all ions.

FIG. 9. Total DPA from all ions, averaged over 10 mm, as a function of depth.

4. Conclusion

Based on the developed model of the VVER-1200 reactor, the neutron spectrum at the inner boundary of the reactor vessel, which has a thickness of 20 cm, has been calculated. Using this spectrum, the parameters of primary knock-on atoms (PKAs) generated by neutron collisions with atoms in the vessel material have been calculated using the MCNP4B program. These parameters were used to create the *TRIM.dat* file for the SRIM/TRIM software. With SRIM/TRIM, the distribution of vacancies in the reactor vessel caused by various ions of atoms within the vessel material has been calculated. The distribution of Displacements Per Atom (DPA) has been calculated based on the computed vacancy distribution. Using this

information, the safe service life of the reactor vessel can be estimated.

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